

Newly Minted Indo-Pacific Politics' Challenges to Decolonising Taiwan's Foreign Relations and Knowledge Production

Abstract

As Taiwan is one of the hotspots of Indo-Pacific politics, its governments, political elites and intellectuals are driving the trend to make Taiwan relevant to the Indo-Pacific. The question here is not whether Taiwan should be part of the Indo-Pacific. Taiwan has no choice. Nevertheless, this article illuminates the difficulties that emerge from the interlocking of *realpolitik* with the production of knowledge, along with the ensuing intersections among Taiwan studies, Indo-Pacific studies, Southeast Asian studies, Austronesian studies, Indigenous studies, and studies of new immigrants as well as relevant imaginaries. These challenges are complex and multi-faceted. This article extends a modest invitation for dialogue and ongoing contemplation regarding this topic. It proposes policy advice with examples to help Taiwanese policymakers, political elites, and educators understand how to incorporate decolonial thinking into their future planning related to the knowledge realm of the Indo-Pacific.

Keywords

Indo-Pacific – Taiwan – knowledge production – decolonisation – Southeast Asia – Austronesian studies

1 Introduction: Indo-Pacific as *Realpolitik* and Knowledge Production

As numerous scholars have accurately noted (e.g. Pan, 2014; Li, 2022), the notion of the Indo-Pacific, along with the associated politics and strategies, are constructed. This term was introduced by the German geopolitician Karl Haushofer in the 1920s, although it did not garner significant attention at that time (Pan, 2014). In the more recent context, it is the American 'geopolitical imagination regarding the world at large and the rise of China specifically' (Pan 2014, 456) that has provided the concept with political significance (Li, 2022). Since the revival of this concept by American, Japanese, and Australian politicians over the past decade, there has been a substantial increase in academic literature examining various countries and regional organisations' policies and strategies towards the Indo-Pacific (Pan, 2014; Medcalf, 2020a and 2020b; Calabrese, 2022; Ghiasy, Chen, and Panda, 2025). Given that Taiwan is a focal point in Indo-Pacific politics, its governments, political leaders, and intellectuals are actively promoting Taiwan's relevance within the Indo-Pacific framework.

The focus of this article, however, is not about Taiwan's Indo-Pacific policies and actions per se. Rather, the focus is on the intersections between *realpolitik* and knowledge production within the context of Taiwan's recent endeavour to get closer to the Indo-Pacific construct. I am inspired by Kemper and Kalinovsky's (2015) use of the concept of 'interlocking' in their studies on Soviet and Russian oriental studies. Hence, I borrow the term interlocking to mean the direct and indirect interactions between different knowledge realms or sub-realms. Taiwan-watchers in Taiwan as well as from the world have contributed greatly to the discussion on the new realm of Indo-Pacific politics. There is a close link between *realpolitik* as well as knowledge production about Indo-Pacific studies and Taiwan studies. Furthermore, as this article will reveal, such intersections are even interlocked with other intersections between *realpolitik* and knowledge production about Southeast Asia, Austronesian studies, indigenous studies, and new immigrant studies. These complicated intersections of knowledge realms and *realpolitik* created different challenges for Taiwan to achieve decolonisation in various ways. Clearly, Taiwan already has different layers of colonial imprints on the island's development. Selective attention to decolonise either European, Chinese, Japanese or American (neo-)colonial influences would lead to the

incomplete decolonisation of knowledge production. This article complicates the matter by checking the rising political currency of the term ‘Indo-Pacific’, both as a *realpolitik* reality and a knowledge realm to be imagined and constructed. When Indo-Pacific intersects with Taiwan, it exacerbates Taiwan’s selective approach to decolonisation.

As Shih (2022) correctly observes, decolonisation necessitates a discourse that does not replicate colonial relationships nor engage in binary thinking (Shih 2022:82). Taiwan historically lost the chance to decolonise when the Chinese Nationalist Party or KMT (國民黨, *guo min dang*) moved to the island in the late 1940s. At that time, the inhabitants of Taiwan had just achieved independence from Japanese rule. This moment could have served as a significant opportunity for the locals to celebrate and properly learn the process of decolonising Taiwan. Nevertheless, the incoming KMT regime was primarily focused on swiftly consolidating power in Taiwan and anticipated that the local Taiwanese would quickly shift their allegiance and exhibit their Chineseness to the new authority, thereby denying them the opportunity to express postcolonial sentiments (Chou, 2024:163; Shih, 2022:76). Since the regime showed little empathy towards the emotions and aspirations of the local elites, these elites sought reconnection with the former colonial power, Japan. Consequently, a sense of nostalgia for the colonial modernity established by Japan emerged (Shih, 2022:78). As long as the KMT was unable to genuinely reclaim the Chinese mainland, which it professed to desire, it could only establish a pseudo-Chinese regime on the island of Taiwan (Shih, 2022). Consequently, the strengthening of ties between local elites and Japan evolved into an intensified aspiration for separate statehood from China. These elites became both anti-KMT and anti-Beijing, relying solely on Japan, the former coloniser, and the United States (US), a figurative neo-coloniser, to shape their Taiwanese identity.

As the Indo-Pacific concept is highly advocated by Japan and the US for geopolitical motives, Taiwan has been drawn further into it (Scott, 2022). It inevitably deepens Taiwan’s connection with Japan and the US. But whatever does not belong to the US-Japan-Taiwan nexus, such as China, becomes the ultimate out-group. The out-group vs in-group thinking is in natural binary and contradicts the basis of the decolonial spirit. The following begins with an elaboration of the challenges generated because of the interlocking between Indo-Pacific politics and various knowledge realms. I then explain why these developments generate several different kinds of problems of decolonisation for Taiwan. Towards the end of the article, I will offer some ideas for reducing these problems.

Method-wise, I mostly use literature review and open-ended interviews and informal conversations with relevant actors, ranging from Taiwan diplomats in Southeast Asian countries to textbook authors, high school teachers, high school students, Indigenous activists, university professors and administrators. These interviews were conducted in Taiwan, Thailand, and Vietnam in 2024 and 2025. Some interviewees prefer anonymity.

What I intend to achieve is to address the potential moral challenges facing policymakers when they are doing Indo-Pacific politics and us scholars when we are writing and producing knowledge about the Indo-Pacific. My aim is to be realistic and practical, pointing out potential moral issues and offering modest guidelines for stakeholders to understand and agree. The proponents and implementers of Indo-Pacific politics rarely mention the moral challenges. If they are ever raised, they are often used by opponents of the Indo-Pacific concepts, such as Chinese or Russian governmental actors and scholars, to undermine the values of the term (Chen, Panda, and Ghiasy, 2024). Clearly, opponents see opportunities to undermine the importance of the Indo-Pacific. Their points might even be valid to some extent. Regardless, I believe that Taiwan and its like-minded allies in world politics are liberal democratic actors

who can comprehend these problems and seek ways to minimise these problems, without altogether jettisoning the term.

2 Interlocking Taiwan, Southeast Asia and Indo-Pacific Politics

Currently, the most common (but not exclusive) way for Taiwan's government, political elites and intellectuals to link Taiwan to the Indo-Pacific is to revise and revive its old Southbound policy, which was created during the KMT era in 1994 (Glaser, Funaiole, and Marston, 2019; Yang, 2018). The original goal was to push for trade and investments in Southeast Asia to diversify Taiwan's over-dependence on its relationship with the People's Republic of China (PRC). In 2016, Tsai Ing-Wen of the Democratic Progress Party or DPP (民進黨, *min jin dang*) administration initiated a New Southbound Policy (NSP). The NSP was considered Tsai's flagship policy. After the January elections in 2024, Lai Ching-Te of the same party was elected the new president. Even though some leaders in the foreign policy circle have changed, the general direction for the NSP to deepen connections with Southeast Asia has not altered. Unlike the old Southbound Policy, NSP pushes for two-way instead of one-way southbound relations. Not only trade, but exchanges between peoples and cultures are emphasised (Chen, 2025). In this context, immigrants from Southeast Asia began to be seen as valuable instruments and bridges for the government's promotion of NSP (Kasai, 2022; Leibold and Chen, 2024). Geographically, the NSP's coverage is wider than the old policy, reaching out to not only Southeast Asia but also South Asia, Australia and New Zealand.¹ While the old policy's focus was on economics, the new NSP's focus is on geopolitics in addition to economics. Furthermore, there is an element of geo-cultural repositioning of Taiwan in that the NSP attempts to create an identity of Taiwan away from its relations with the PRC. In other words, instead of focusing solely on bilateral economic ties between Taiwan and the PRC, this new policy aims to further Taiwan's people-to-people and societal bonds with Southeast Asia, South Asia, and even Australia and New Zealand (Scott, 2019; Tsai, 2022; Lee and Chan, 2023; Chen, 2025).

While it is true that the NSP geographically covers more regions and countries than the older policy, it is undeniable that most observers still see Southeast Asia as the primary focus of Taiwan (Glaser, Funaiole, and Marston, 2019; Yang, 2018; Effendi, 2025). The reason is three-fold. First, Southeast Asia is historically connected to the Chinese diaspora, and Taiwan's involvement in it has a long history. Second, Southeast Asia is one of the pivotal geographic locations in the world where Taiwan's government and intellectual elites have strived to make a *longue durée* connection via the so-called Austronesian concept. According to various narratives about the Austronesian peoples, they are believed to have lived in Taiwan for eight thousand years. Taiwan is believed to be where the Austronesians migrated from to the Philippines and then to mainland Southeast Asia and the islands of Indonesia (Marinaccio, 2021).

The above reasons show that Southeast Asia is the region where Taiwan's government and elites can 'hit two birds with one stone'. Deepening relations with Southeast Asia allows Taiwan to continue its efforts to distance itself from the PRC economically, culturally and identity-wise. It also enables the Austronesian narrative to continue to substantiate, which similarly distances Taiwan's history and identity further away from the PRC.

Lastly, Southeast Asia also brings in new immigration that the DPP administrations have instrumentally used to present a multicultural Taiwan (Effendi, 2025). Taiwan receives more immigrants from Southeast Asia than any other broadly defined Indo-Pacific region, such as South Asia, Australia and New Zealand. In the multicultural framework that some of Taiwan's elites and government seek to

¹ Eighteen countries are presently included: Thailand, Indonesia, the Philippines, Malaysia, Singapore, Brunei, Vietnam, Myanmar, Cambodia, Laos, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Bhutan, Australia and New Zealand.

promote, China is only a facet of Taiwan's new society and new reality. That is why Taiwan's government and elites can even 'hit three birds with one stone' with their policy focus on Southeast Asia.

Because of the geopolitical origin of the Indo-Pacific concept, publications on Taiwan's Indo-Pacific relations are generated mainly by researchers and public intellectuals who specialise in international relations and politics in Taiwan. Think tanks are the main drivers for producing knowledge, including bodies such as the Taiwan-Asia Exchange Foundation, the Prospect Foundation and the Institute for National Defense and Security Research (e.g. Wang and Hsiao, 2021). Some of the publications and events that these think tanks have created are centred on Taiwan's relations with India, Southeast Asia or Japan. For example, founded in 2018, the Taiwan-Asian Exchange Foundation holds an annual Yushan Forum to foster exchanges between societal leaders within the remit of the NSP. The Prospect Foundation similarly holds a regular Indo-Pacific Security Dialogue event co-organised with other think tanks from Taiwan and abroad (Yang and Hashmi, 2022).

For Taiwan, the NSP is seen as a vital but not the only connecting point. For example, Taiwan and the US launched a Global Cooperation and Training Framework in 2015, with Japan and Australia participating. They organise events to share experiences and exchange information on issues that concern them collectively (Website of Global Cooperation and Training Framework, 2025). This framework's cooperative partners are from all over the world and are not limited to NSP countries.

The events occurring at these geopolitical levels influence the trajectory of research and educational institutions, as these entities have strategically adopted the term Indo-Pacific in their initiatives, with the intention of showcasing the relevance of their research to current issues and in hopes of securing funding for their operations. This should not be unexpected. Historically, even during the announcement of the old Southbound policy in 1994, Taiwan's Academia Sinica, the most prestigious research institution on the island, established the Programme for Southeast Asian Area Studies. Michael Hsin Huang Hsiao, a prominent Taiwanese scholar advocating for Taiwan's identity, led the Southeast Asian Area Studies programme at Academia Sinica. This programme was recognised as the first research-oriented institution for Southeast Asian studies in Taiwan. It was subsequently merged and reorganised, leading to the present-day Centre for Asia-Pacific Area Studies, which focuses on maritime studies and Southeast Asia, among other topics (Ku, 2006). It is important to highlight that Hsiao also serves as the chairperson of the Taiwan-Asia Exchange Foundation, which is currently assisting in the promotion of the NSP.

In the realm of educational institutions, in response to the old Southbound policy, Tamkang University located in northern Taiwan established a Graduate Institute of Southeast Asian Studies in 1996, marking it as the first of its kind in Taiwan. Subsequently, in 1997, the National Chi-Nan University situated in Nantou, Central Taiwan, also initiated a Graduate School of Southeast Asian Studies along with a Centre for Southeast Asian Studies (Chen, 2025). Furthermore, in southern Taiwan, both the National Sun Yat-Sen University in Kaohsiung and the National Cheng Kung University in Tainan founded a Centre for Southeast Asian Studies at the onset of the 21st century (Ku, 2006). Currently, with the emergence of the newly established Indo-Pacific concept, each of these institutions has exhibited varying degrees of integration with it through their events and publications. Nevertheless, at the time this article was written, they seem to maintain a primary focus on their traditional area studies on Southeast Asia. Publications concerning Indo-Pacific subjects are still largely produced by think tanks engaged in foreign policy and international relations.

Through the NSP, Taiwan's research and educational institutions have been motivated to establish stronger connections with NSP countries (Lin and Yang, 2024; Yen, 2024). They have demonstrated their ingenuity by applying for government funding to facilitate their NSP-related activities. For example, National Chi-Nan University successfully applied for and received a grant from the Ministry of Education aimed at training language teachers to be proficient in Southeast Asian languages (Chen, 2025). Consequently, doctoral students from Southeast Asian nations can be trained to instruct in high schools

and universities across Taiwan. This initiative not only provides job opportunities for Southeast Asian students but also enhances the capacity of Taiwan's educational institutions to offer Southeast Asian language courses (Chen, 2025).

In Northern Taiwan, National Cheng-Chi University initiated a bachelor's programme in 2017 aimed at teaching Southeast Asian languages and cultures, particularly focusing on Vietnamese, Thai, and Indonesian studies. This programme was officially upgraded to become the Department of Southeast Asian Languages and Cultures in 2024. National Cheng-Chi University employs educators directly from Southeast Asia to provide instruction about the region, thereby reducing reliance on Western or Taiwanese teachers whose perspectives may be influenced by Western or Taiwanese epistemology (Chao, 2025).

Consequently, Taiwan's ability to comprehend and study Southeast Asia has significantly improved compared to previous decades. The initiative to attract talent from Southeast Asia is also proving successful. An increasing number of students from Southeast Asian countries—including Vietnam, Indonesia, and Malaysia—are enrolling in Taiwanese institutions, thereby surpassing the number of students from the Chinese Mainland, Macao, and Hong Kong, who have traditionally been a major source of international students. This shift indicates a diversification away from the Chinese market in the recruitment of international students (Website of Ministry of Education of Taiwan, 2024a; Huang, 2025).

3 Adding the Austronesian Layer

Another knowledge realm that is currently not officially included within the construct of Taiwan's NSP and the Indo-Pacific which is being debated, is the field of Austronesian Studies. Even before the arrival of the Indo-Pacific construct, Taiwan's government and intellectual elites have promoted Austronesian Studies to generate apprehension of Taiwan's prehistory Austronesian heritage with its Indigenous population, repositioning Taiwan as a nation in the Asia-Pacific and thus distancing itself from its Chinese connection (Huang, 2022). Some researchers have argued that the NSP should also geographically cover Pacific islands due to their shared Austronesian heritage and that Taiwan has previously engaged in various exchanges with the Pacific islands (Jiang, Sun, Bao and Chen, 2018; Jerzewski, 2021). Since other like-minded countries (e.g. the US, South Korea) have covered the Pacific islands in their Indo-Pacific strategies, some researchers and policy advisors in Taiwan argue that Taiwan's NSP should cover them too (Jiang, Sun, Bao and Chen, 2018; Jerzewski, 2021). Even so, we have yet to see this materialised in terms of foreign policy adjustment and, subsequently, recalibration of knowledge realms, interlocking Taiwan studies more closely with other relevant fields in Indo-Pacific politics, Southeast Asian studies, Austronesian studies and Indigenous studies.

This is a progress in formation. One can find examples of such kind of interlocking gradually taking place, at least within the intellectual circle. For instance, there was an academic event, 'Sense of Place and Transculturality International Conference' at the National Taiwan Normal University in May 2025. The conference was hosted by the National Taiwan Normal University's Department of Taiwan Culture, Languages and Literature and sponsored by Taiwan's Ministry of Education. The central theme of this conference is about the literature, cultures and language education in Taiwan and Southeast Asia. In the call for papers for the conference, it is indicated that sub-themes such as Austronesian culture, Indigenous issues and new immigration are relevant topics because of the intersection between Taiwan and Southeast Asia in these domains (Website of the Department of Taiwan Culture, Languages and Literature, 2025). The interplay of imaginaries such as Taiwan studies, Southeast Asia studies, Austronesian (and Indigenous) studies and new immigrant studies is vivid in the conference call. The sponsorship from Taiwan's government manifests its preference for backing initiatives that can deepen the interlocking of these knowledge realms.

However, even if deeper interlocking were to take place, there would be critiques about such kind of state-led or top-down approach. This is because enlisting the Indigenous (Austronesian) heritage for geopolitical interests does not necessarily reflect Indigenous peoples' views and interests (Simon, 2020; Huang 2022). Scott E. Simon (2025) has explained that Indigenous peoples should be seen as small nations on their own. Instead of fitting into Taiwan's multicultural idea, it is important to recognise that Indigenous peoples have their own unique rights and traditions. Understanding them in this way helps to honour their history and contributions, showing that they are more than just part of a larger society.

For instance, the Siraya are an Indigenous group located in southwest Taiwan who engaged in significant contact with Dutch colonizers and Han Chinese communities during the 17th century (Adelaar, 2013; Brown, 2004; Joby, 2025). In a 2025 conversation with Edgar Macapili and Uma Talavan, two prominent activists promoting the Siraya language, culture, and rights in Taiwan, they shared that while they understand the term 'Austronesian' as an academic construct, they also recognise its strategic use by the Taiwanese government to foster diplomatic ties with countries that identify as part of the Austronesian family. Macapili and Talavan (2025) explained that they do not oppose this conceptual framing; in fact, they find it helpful as a bridge for understanding their people's roots and as a tool in their broader struggle for recognition and Indigenous rights.

Interestingly, Edgar Macapili, originally from the Philippines, discovered strong parallels between his Indigenous Bisayan language and his wife Uma's Siraya language. Both languages belong to the Austronesian language family. The couple has since become central figures in the revival of the Siraya language and cultural identity in Taiwan—a cause deeply rooted in Uma Talavan's family legacy. Their personal journey illustrates the tangible and emotional reality of the Austronesian connection between Taiwan and Southeast Asia.

At the same time, Macapili and Talavan (2025) observed that a disconnect often exists between the academic and political use of the 'Austronesian' label and how actual Indigenous communities perceive and experience their identities. Even within the same Indigenous group, sub-groups may take diverging stances: some embrace the label for strategic access to government support, while others distance themselves from it to maintain a sense of local authenticity. This diversity of views is rarely acknowledged or respected by policymakers and scholars. The problem, they argue, is not necessarily the use of the term itself, but the top-down imposition of such identity frameworks without careful attention to the lived nuances and self-understandings of the communities involved. This failure to listen stands in tension with decolonial principles.

These complexities are not unique to Taiwan. During the author's separate discussion with an anonymous scholar from the Iban group in Malaysia in 2025, the individual expressed skepticism toward the academic claim that Taiwan is the 'birthplace' of Austronesian languages and peoples. Although the Iban language is clearly classified as Austronesian, the scholar's resistance illustrates the discomfort that some Indigenous groups feel when external narratives appear to redefine or challenge their own rootedness in their ancestral lands.

Nevertheless, academic research—especially in linguistics and archaeology—has provided substantial evidence that the greatest diversity of Austronesian languages is found in Taiwan (e.g., Blust 1984-1985). According to Macapili (2025), this linguistic concentration suggests that Proto-Austronesian likely originated in Taiwan before spreading southward through the Philippines and into the Pacific and Southeast Asia, with decreasing diversity along the migratory route. He explains that this model does not undermine the identities of Indigenous groups elsewhere but can enrich their understanding of shared ancestry without negating local heritage.

Supporting this view are archaeological findings associated with the Lapita cultural complex, which dates to around 1500 BCE (Macapili, 2025). While Lapita culture itself likely developed in the Bismarck Archipelago, its emergence was shaped by maritime and material innovations traceable to Taiwan and

the northern Philippines. Pottery styles and seafaring technologies consistent with Austronesian expansion suggest a broad migratory trajectory from north to south (Macapili, 2025). Furthermore, genetic studies reveal that many Austronesian-speaking populations share genetic markers with Indigenous Taiwanese groups, although these markers become increasingly mixed as populations interacted with others across Southeast Asia (Macapili, 2025).

Macapili (2025) emphasizes that the Austronesian expansion was not a simple, one-directional migration but a dynamic process marked by interaction, adaptation, and cultural synthesis. Rather than a singular narrative of the Austronesian origin, it is more accurate to speak of a shared heritage. Many Southeast Asian Indigenous groups significantly shaped the development of Austronesian culture through their own contributions, rituals, and technologies. Their resistance to a single ‘homeland’ narrative may stem from a valid desire to assert their longstanding presence in their territories.

In Macapili’s (2025) view, resistance to the Taiwan-as-homeland theory often arises from a mistaken equivalence between linguistic and genetic descent. Macapili explains that recognizing the linguistic origins of Austronesian in Taiwan does not imply that all modern speakers are genetically descended from ancient Taiwanese peoples. As linguist Sami Honkasalo (2025) points out, the movement of languages does not mirror the movement of genes; for example, the widespread use of English in Africa or India does not mean English speakers there are genetically Anglo-Saxon. Clarifying this distinction can ease tensions and help local communities understand that linguistic connections need not threaten their deep roots in their own lands.

To navigate these sensitivities and avoid oversimplification, Macapili (2025) advocates for deeper collaboration between disciplines—linguistics, anthropology, archaeology, and genetics, to construct a more holistic, evidence-based understanding of Austronesian migration. Such an interdisciplinary approach would reduce academic and political distortions and foster respectful dialogue with Indigenous communities throughout the region.

Moreover, towards the Pacific islands, there have been critiques about Taiwan’s one-way wish to link itself to other perceived Austronesian groups in the Pacific without appreciating that each Pacific Island country has its own national identity and interest (Marinaccio, 2021; Huang, 2022). Marinaccio’s (2021) study of various peoples from Pacific Island countries shows that locals do not necessarily understand that they are Austronesian. In Taiwan, the intertwining of Austronesian language, culture and ethnicity, along with the terms Austronesia(n), Pacific and Indigenous, arises from the understanding that regions such as New Zealand, Guam and Hawai’i—settler colonies like Taiwan—exhibit similar institutions, concepts of indigeneity and even shared ancestral connections. Consequently, while Taiwan’s Austronesian diplomacy is generally directed towards all Pacific nations, it holds particular significance for non-allied Pacific settler colonies only (Marinaccio, 2021).

Even if these linkages were ostensibly made between Taiwan and some selected Pacific islands, there would still be a profound challenge in how local lay people in Taiwan find themselves relating to these concepts. Marinaccio’s (2021) study indicates that some segments of the Taiwanese population express disdain or discrimination against Pacific communities, such as looking at them as lazy and backward. Overall, the Austronesian concept remains an exercise for policymakers, political elites and intellectuals, and they tend to conflate many notions into one (Marinaccio, 2021). The adverse domestic repercussions, as shown in local Taiwanese people’s discrimination against Pacific communities, raise further inquiries about the effectiveness of the Austronesian discourse and the imaginary (Marinaccio, 2021).

As previously mentioned, certain scholars proposing ideas for policymaking (e.g., Jiang, Sun, Bao, and Chen, 2018; Jerzewski, 2021) have argued that the Austronesian aspect should be more closely linked to Taiwan’s Indo-Pacific relations. The NSP countries do not encompass Pacific Island nations. However, for example, the state-led Council of Indigenous Peoples (2019) does associate the NSP with its various activities related to Pacific Islands. The interactions among the government, intellectuals, and civil

societies are evident. Nevertheless, their efforts primarily reinforce the normalcy of Taiwan's sovereignty as a state. This reflects the interests of the increasing population's concerns regarding Taiwan's statehood. There is little interest in perceiving Taiwan as a settler nation and in taking broader measures to ensure that indigenous issues can transcend the state framework (Huang 2022; Chou 2024).

To sum up the above different directions of development, they arise out of the context of some Taiwanese elites' aspiration for further de-sinicisation and yearning to be more active in the US-Japan-led Indo-Pacific politics at the international level. The de-sinicisation aspect refers to the fact that many of Taiwan's current policies are driven by motives of creating and enshrining its own distinct identity apart from China. The process started with Taiwanisation or indigenisation already during the KMT's time and evolved further to become de-sinicisation during various DPP administrations (Chang, 2004; Lams and Liao, 2011; Leibold and Chen, 2025). A discourse of Taiwan subjectivity has been developed, and we can see that a Taiwan-centric worldview or cultural and educational policies prioritising a Taiwan-centric view have become common. While the process does help decolonise Taiwan from the Chinese sphere of knowledge production, at the same time, the measures taken to achieve de-sinicisation have pushed Taiwan closer to a metaphorical colonial dependence on the US and Japan, hindering Taiwan's genuine decolonisation from its geopolitical past, present and future. Here I wonder if a decolonial project is strongly identity-based, will it create new kinds of epistemic injustice and inequality?

What might be even worse is that to make these new concepts work, Taiwan has to project a neo-colonial imagination on its relations with countries in Southeast Asia or the Pacific islands. These politically motivated selections of relations are understandable from geopolitical perspectives. Nevertheless, they leave many questions about how Taiwan itself and all the people living there can genuinely decolonise its foreign relations and how it can uphold the principle of decolonisation in its various policy domains.

Clearly, these problems are not just results of (neo)colonial mindsets. Other factors, such as uninformed decision-making, neo-liberalism, electoral politics, unresolved internal debates, limited resources, and others, have contributed to these problems too (e.g., Sugimoto, 2018; Simon, 2020 and 2025; Silan, Baine, and Wang, 2024). These issues have been covered by other studies. As space is limited, I have opted not to elaborate further, but it is vital to point out the complexity of the challenges ahead, and with this, I intend to move on to the second major part of this paper, that is, to encourage thoughts on how to improve the situation in practices.

4 Geopolitical Policies Should Take Decolonial Thoughts into Design

Taiwan cannot avoid the term 'Indo-Pacific' in its external relations. If Taiwan must choose between two priorities, geopolitical affiliation with the Indo-Pacific versus decolonisation of foreign relations, *realpolitik* will always win. While Taiwan cannot do without further engaging with Indo-Pacific politics, Taiwan, as a democratic liberal society that yearns for value-based diplomacy, should make sure that the spirit of decolonisation is more salient in its policy formation. The following ideas for Indo-Pacific politics can be applied to other countries that are advocating for this term, such as Japan as well. Maybe this can be seen as a kind of Indo-Pacific policy 2.0 or 3.0 or an ethical Indo-Pacific policy.

Beyond these bumper stickers, anyway, the essence is to redress the elements that are counter decolonial spirits. Decolonisation cannot redo what has been done, but decolonial gestures or policy implementation considering the decolonial spirit can be manifested. To uphold the principles of decolonisation, we should first discern different kinds of decolonial priorities for the colonisers (shorthand as Group A here) and the colonised (shorthand as Group B here). It is vital to note that in the context of this article's discussion, the concepts of colonisers and colonised are metaphorical, but they

do have policy consequences. The metaphorical colonised subjects may be people in Southeast Asia (or other NSP countries), Indigenous peoples in Taiwan, people in countries that may be considered Austronesian (which may include both settler colonisers and Indigenous peoples in these countries) and new immigrants and their offsprings in Taiwan. In decolonial principles, the colonised subjects, Group B, should take their own affairs, voices and future into their own hands, maximising self-determination and autonomy. Their awakening to being appropriated as part of Taiwan's Indo-Pacific, plus many imaginary things, is thus essential. The aforesaid activists for the Sirayan people and culture, Macapili and Talavan (2025) are hopeful examples of Group B with awareness and motivation for self-determination.

My proposal here focuses on the priorities of those who are metaphorically enforcing a colonial mindset and practices, that is, Group A. Group A is composed primarily of policymakers and political and intellectual elites in Taiwan. They should carefully and critically reflect on the current situation. The foundational guideline for decolonisation would then direct Group A to make a conscious endeavour to prioritise and learn about Group B's perspectives, interests and voices. The following three elements should be fostered and practiced by Group A. I owe these ideas to scholars working on the decolonisation and Indigenous rights (Silan and Munkejord, 2023; Silan, Baine, and Wang, 2024), and I apply similar principles to the case study here.

- 1) Group A should harbour cultural humility to be willing to actively listen to Group B's voices and critically reflect on their ideas and mutual differences. The process will lead to the unlearning of some existing views of Group B.
- 2) Group A should not automatically assume that Group B would agree with and appreciate Group A's interests, such as some segments of Taiwan's people's geopolitical interests, aspiration to showcase a successful multicultural society or aspiration to de-sinicise.
- 3) Critical allyship would involve Group A's strong association with Group B as a sign of dedication to contribute meaningful change aimed at redressing the inequality and injustice that has been reinforced by Group A on Group B.

With these elements in mind, we now see how they can apply to different kinds of people in Group A. One type of Group A people would be primarily governmental officials, think tank analysts, political observers and international relations experts who are at the frontline of constructing Taiwan's meaningful participation in Indo-Pacific politics and knowledge realm. Their meetings and workshops should add discussion on decolonisation. It is common that international relations experts have near zero background knowledge about decolonisation (Krishna, 2012). This is not just in Taiwan but also elsewhere in the world. Funding for Indo-Pacific purposes should be allocated to support workshops that bring international relations experts to meet scholars and activists working on decolonisation. The objective is to have dialogue and cultivate Group A's decolonial literacy and capacity. More advanced workshops should then add representatives of Group B to brainstorm together, forming policies that meet the principles of decolonisation. The expected outcome would be that Group A would genuinely carry out the three aforesaid elements and further modify existing Indo-Pacific narratives to clearly show that they are not reproducing any metaphorical or real (neo)colonial relations (Table 1).

The decolonial principle is to ask whether the policy can work beyond binary views to cope with the complexity of relationships (e.g. foreign relations), respect the local Indigenous voices, empower the weak and redress epistemic inequality and injustice. One also must be careful to avoid the oppressed side becoming the oppressors in the context of decolonial endeavours. Apparently, this will be a daunting task as in Taiwan, projects like these most likely will be conflated with Taiwan's divisive identity politics, hindering meaningful progress. In the previous section, I noted the complexity of the challenges ahead already (see also Table 1 below). Careful design to avoid this trap at the outset is crucial.

Another type of Group A people (hereafter referred to as Group A-1) should be government officials, scholars, think tank experts and political observers who are active in fostering Taiwan’s increasing nexus with Southeast Asia. The uniqueness of Southeast Asia and why it deserves special attention have been elaborated previously (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Decolonial elements in actions

	Cultural humility	Avoid assumptions that Group B would appreciate and agree with Group A’s interests	Critical allyship	Potential obstacles in addition to common challenge of neo-liberal managerialism	Potential strategies to overcome obstacles
Group A: Those working in international relations	Workshop to learn about decolonisation	Workshop to learn about Group B’s (e.g. Southeast Asians, Pacific islanders) views	Advanced workshop to formulate policy adjustments together	The spillover effect from Taiwan’s identity politics	
Group A-1: Those working to foster links between Taiwan and Southeast Asia	Ditto	Ditto	Ditto		
	Ideally, this should be reflected in K-12 education. But K-12 education has not done much in textbooks and actual learning.		Lacking and hard to create	Exam-oriented culture; a decrease in overall learning hours	Increase the proportion in curriculum and textbooks
	Mother tongue classes		Lacking and hard to create	State-led instrumentalism	Train and hire more Southeast Asians to teach
Group A-2: Media producers	Media portrayal is either overly negative or positive but with homogenous narration		Lacking and hard to create	Media competition, which drives an increase in sensational (negative) news or state-led instrumentalism that results in homogenous positive narrative	-Respect that Group B owns their voices and reflect their diverse voices in the media -Real people-to-people exchange to break stereotypes

SOURCE: CREATED BY THE AUTHOR WITH INSPIRATION FROM RESEARCH ON INDIGENOUS STUDIES (e.g., Silan, Baine, and Wang, 2024)

Workshops to learn about decolonialisation and tailored to the understanding of Southeast Asia and local views can be similarly organised for Group A-1 people. Currently, from the governmental to the societal levels in Taiwan, people harbour a lot of biased and misunderstanding of Southeast Asia. One example is that higher education institutions and Taiwan's government need to update their knowledge about the nature of Southeast Asian students. The old understanding from Taiwan is that Southeast Asian students are from economically developing countries and thus need financial support if Taiwan wishes to attract their students. There are nowadays more and more middle-class Southeast Asian students who might not be able to afford Western education and have looked increasingly at Taiwan as an economically viable location for quality education. They do not necessarily need financial support from Taiwan. However, they do need to have contact points from Taiwan to help them understand and select suitable educational paths in Taiwan. Taiwanese higher education institutions should allocate resources to visit Southeast Asian universities and meet their students directly to set up contact points. On-campus visits are more effective in the successful recruitment of Southeast Asian students than simply joining educational fairs. A successful example is Ming Chuan University's close working relations with the University of Thai Chamber of Commerce to offer international degree and non-degree study programmes, such as international business, fashion, etc., directly in Bangkok. Through this, every year, Ming Chuan University was able to directly recruit around one thousand students from their education centre in Bangkok to study at Ming Chuan University in Taiwan (Qin 2025).

While experts in Group A-1 need workshops to advance their capacity in decolonial practices, they also need to use their learnt capacity to reform Taiwan's K-12 education, including primary school, junior high school and senior high school education (Table 1). Taiwan's K-12 curriculum design does not typically consider international situations because they change too fast. Hence, the term 'Indo-Pacific' is not covered in the curriculum.

In the 2019 curriculum (Website of Ministry of Education, 2019), it is stipulated that authors of textbooks can choose to focus on either Southeast Asia or South Asia. Despite this, the proportions of Southeast Asia and South Asia in curriculum and textbooks do not increase. High school textbooks do not cover Indo-Pacific or NSP at all. Junior high school textbooks mention Southeast Asia, but the percentage is little, and often placed as a learning exercise after the main text in textbooks (Lay, 2025). The general trend is that the learning hours of geography and other compulsory studies are decreasing. This decline is related to Taiwan's educational reform to allocate more time for students to learn and relax freely.

Anonymous high school teachers and students whom I have talked to expressed that there are very few class hours allocated to learn about topics on Indigenous peoples, Southeast Asia or new immigrants from Southeast Asia. Such topics might be covered in 'civil education', not in history textbooks. The anonymous teacher also expressed that current textbooks are arranged differently from generations ago. Instead of a linear historical introduction, the lessons focus on issues. So, Southeast Asia and other relevant matters may be covered in these topical lessons but not in detail. When it comes to sensitive and controversial issues like Taiwan's divisive identity politics and integration of new immigrants, teachers usually avoid further discussion and simply present some descriptive facts. One also must bear in mind that in Taiwan's context, very often, students and teachers only focus on issues that would be covered in exams, particularly national exams, to enter universities. Due to these obstacles, Taiwan's primary and high school education turns out not to be the primary source where citizens can learn and contemplate vital issues of national identities, Indigenous peoples and new immigrants (Table 1).

Anonymous students whom I talked to mentioned that they mainly gain knowledge about these contentious issues from family or the media. In Table 1, I thus list media producers as Group A-2. Formosa TV in Taiwan, for example, has regular reports of (positive) examples of both Southeast Asian

and mainland Chinese immigrations' integration into Taiwan's society. Nevertheless, the challenge is that sometimes, an overly homogenous narrative framework is used to reflect state-sanctioned multicultural views on immigration. The story is usually about an immigrant's struggle, but with hard work, they manage to find their place in Taiwan. While it is in line with the decolonial spirit to let immigrants speak out and offer personal testimonies in the media, Taiwanese media may further advance the decolonial spirit if they provide more space for immigrants to freely share their stories beyond standardised or institutionalised narrative (Table 1).

It is worth noting that, in terms of proportion, positive narration is less than negative narration in the media (Table 1). More than one anonymous interviewee engaging in Southeast Asian studies stresses that Taiwan's society and people still have a lot of misunderstanding of Southeast Asia, often through intermediated knowledge (usually negative) gained from the media. Crimes, poverty and danger are frequently associated with news about Southeast Asia and their immigrants in Taiwan. A bit similar to the aforementioned Pacific communities' issues, some segments of Taiwan's population harbour disdain and discrimination against people from Southeast Asia. Overall, the public in Taiwan is generally still not as positive about Southeast Asia as it is about Japan or the US. This also have implications for higher education. For example, Taiwan's Ministry of Education has scholarships for Taiwanese students to study in Southeast Asian countries. However, there are not many applications per year, even though the Ministry has tried to secure a quota for those willing to study there (excluding Singapore, Australia and New Zealand, see example in Table 2).

TABLE 2 Partial Ministry of Education scholarships granted to Taiwanese students to study abroad

Year	15 NSP Countries Excluding Australia, New Zealand, and Singapore	Australia, New Zealand, and Singapore	Other countries
2013	0		162
2014	2		155
2015	3		148
2016	0		154
2017	6	7	169
2018	1	10	166
2019	3	15	156
2020	2	11	168
2021	6	11	174
2022	2	12	172
2023	1	11	173
2024	0	10	170

SOURCE: WEBSITE OF MINISTRY OF EDUCATION OF TAIWAN (2024b); COLLECTED AND REORGANISED BY THE AUTHOR.

Another noteworthy fact returning to the issue of education, is that since 2019, the curriculum has started to teach the languages of new immigrants. This inclusion reflects the generational change whereby immigrant children are now part of Taiwan's society and wish to explore their hybrid identity in multicultural Taiwan and be recognised. In elementary schools, there is a native tongue policy where mother tongues such as Taiwanese and Hakka, as well as the languages of new Southeast Asian immigrants, are supposed to be offered. Despite being paved with good intentions, these policies are still criticised by rights groups that the Taiwanese government simply pays lip service without putting more effort into truly elevating immigrants' rights and helping them integrate meaningfully into society. Some scholars also have criticised this kind of instrumental approach to enhancing Taiwan's multiculturalism (Lan, 2019; Zemanek and Momesso, 2023). To improve the situation as we advance, some good

practices need to be expanded. As said, National Chi-Nan University trains Southeast Asian doctoral students to become language teachers in Taiwan's high schools and universities (Chen, 2025). This is a positive example that can be replicated to allow Taiwanese students to have direct contact with Southeast Asian teachers and to learn from them. At the higher education level, National Cheng-Chi University's recruitment of Southeast Asian faculty members to develop their Southeast Asian studies is also an encouraging example. The practice needs to shift towards a more substantial form of inclusion of Southeast Asians and immigrants from Southeast Asia to participate in knowledge production about Southeast Asia in Taiwan.

While Table 1 summarises the problems and ideas to overcome the problems caused by Group A, to be fair, I should mention that misunderstanding and lack of understanding between Taiwan and NSP societies is mutual. Stereotypes and biases about Taiwan and its people also exist in Southeast Asian countries where lay people have only little or incomplete knowledge about Taiwan. An anonymous interviewee shared that Thai people have a point-like understanding of Taiwan, such as bubble tea or Taiwan's bad relations with China. Again, the media most likely has contributed to this kind of knowledge. The knowledge asymmetries and gaps between Taiwan and Southeast Asia (not to even mention other NSP countries) are vast. As we all know, knowledge production interacts with and is shaped by different forces. While we might not be able to shift the dynamics of knowledge production completely to become more balanced, we owe it to ourselves to ameliorate the situation. For instance, when Taiwan and Thailand waive each other's visas, it becomes easier for citizens from both sides to visit each other and gain knowledge and on-site experience to break mediated knowledge and imagination of one another. An anonymous interviewee mentioned that when museums in Taiwan and Thailand exchanged exhibitions to show their respective minority peoples' tattoo cultures in 2019, people from both sides were brought closer to each other (Taiwan Today, 2019). One must acknowledge that people-to-people and cultural understanding are like seeds that need time to nurture and grow beyond politics and election cycles.

It is also important to note that Taiwan's government has tried to implement projects, particularly in support of decolonisation. Even so, neo-liberal ways of managing these projects, over-stressing micro-management and performance indicators, have paradoxically worked against decolonial spirits (Silan et al., 2024). This is a common problem facing many grant-giving institutions around the world nowadays, whereas outcome metrics and impact evaluations are overly stressed. Several studies have pointed out that if decolonial projects run on the neo-liberal paradigm, they cannot redress issues of power inequality and thus dilute the effects of decolonising efforts (Bell, Yukich, Lythberg, and Woods, 2022; Silan, Baine, and Wang, 2024).

5 Conclusion: Towards an Ethical Indo-Pacific Policy

Taiwan's Ministry of Education has played a pivotal role in driving educational reforms and distributing resources to sectors related to Southeast Asia.² Simultaneously, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, along with think tanks and various research institutions, has spearheaded the overall advancement of knowledge pertaining to the Indo-Pacific region. The following points are proposed to these actors to improve in line with the decolonial spirit.

² Taiwan's Ministry of Education website (2021 and 2024) contains information about how it links education policy to NSP. For instance, it created the New Southbound Talent Development Programme targeting Southeast Asian and South Asia countries to expand Taiwan's higher education market overseas and promote interflows of talented people between Taiwan and NSP countries.

- The Ministry of Foreign Affairs and relevant think tanks should allocate resources to train international relations experts in literacy in decolonisation and brainstorm foreign policies that narrate Taiwan's Indo-Pacific engagement more in line with decolonial principles. Decolonising methodologies and logic ought to be incorporated into both the grant application procedures and the project content that pertains to Indo-Pacific political issues.
- Taiwan's government needs to update their understanding of Southeast Asian countries and the needs of contemporary Southeast Asian students if they wish to attract talent to Taiwan.
- Curriculum reform should proportionally increase understanding of NSP countries and raise awareness that the media might generate biased information about these countries and their people.
- The Ministry of Education and universities should expand funding to train and hire Indigenous Southeast Asian experts.
- The media's very nature makes it easy to create stereotypes and myths. Media producers should be trained to understand the value of non-homogenous ways of narrating Southeast Asia and Southeast Asian immigrants and include more Southeast Asians in their media reports.
- There are other ways and players to help break the mediated knowledge and imagination about NSP countries, such as through people-to-people exchange. Government funding should support creative solutions to mediate the media effect.
- Funding applicants and receivers should continue to give feedback to grant-givers to decolonise projects that support decolonialisation but heavily run on neo-liberal principles.

Taiwan can be and should be a norm-maker or norm-organiser—by integrating decolonial principles into its domestic and external policies; it can make itself another role model for many other like-minded democratic countries that wish to uphold and conduct value-based diplomacy and be a responsible player in the international system.

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